
Introducing High School Students to Historical Network Research: A Pedagogical Framework

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Abstract

This short paper presents the course Introduction to Historical Network Research as a framework for fostering future researchers in network analysis with an emphasis on historical applications. This initiative builds on prior high school scientific initiation projects employing databases, the ePistolarium platform, and custom data processing tools to introduce foundational Historical Network Research (HNR) concepts. The course is structured to provide theoretical and practical skills to high school students. The course begins with core principles of network science, such as nodes, edges, and centrality measures (Newman, 2010), progressing to applications in HNR supported by tools like Gephi and NetworkX. Historical datasets highlight key research techniques, such as ego network construction and the analysis of the circulation of knowledge. Drawing from Graham et al. (2016), the course situates HNR within the broader context of digital humanities, emphasizing its interdisciplinary potential. Kerschbaumer et al. (2021) highlight the key role of visualization and analytical techniques in HNR, emphasizing its importance in interpreting complex historical phenomena. This perspective aligns with the course's focus on equipping participants with practical tools for effectively exploring and visualizing historical networks. Earlier projects have demonstrated the viability of this approach, showing how HNR methods can illuminate the student's knowledge about historical episodes while fostering computational proficiency. Past projects with high school students included exploring correspondence networks in the 17th-century Dutch Republic and creating small custom programs to preprocess data for network analysis (Silva, Pinto, & Alcantara, 2021). These experiences validate the design of the course, ensuring it addresses both the technical and theoretical needs of its participants. Preliminary outcomes indicate that the course effectively bridges the gap between computational tools and historical inquiry, encouraging a deeper understanding of the relational dynamics of historical phenomena. Challenges remain in ensuring accessibility for participants with diverse backgrounds and balancing technical depth with conceptual clarity. The course serves as a replicable model for integrating HNR into broader educational settings, promoting students' interest in participating in research projects.

References:

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